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ADMINISTRATIVE PRACTICES IN DELEGATING DUTIES AND THEIR EFFECTS ON JOB SATISFACTION OF ACADEMIC STAFF IN CROSS RIVER UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: This study examined the relationship between administrators' politics of delegation of responsibilities and academic staff job satisfaction in universities located in Cross River State, Nigeria. Guided by two research questions and tested through two hypotheses, the study employed a correlational research design. The population comprised 141 heads of departments from two public universities in the state, all of whom were included using a census sampling technique. Data were collected through a specially developed questionnaire titled Administrators' Politics of Delegation of Responsibilities and Academic Staff Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (APDRASSQ), which was validated by experts in higher education administration and measurement and evaluation. Statistical analysis using Pearson's product-moment correlation revealed a significant positive relationship between administrators' delegation of responsibilities and the job satisfaction levels of academic staff. The findings underscore the importance of effective delegation practices by university administrators as a means of enhancing academic staff satisfaction, which is crucial for institutional success and staff productivity. The study recommends that university management should adopt transparent and inclusive delegation strategies to foster a more satisfying work environment for academic personnel.

Keywords: Delegation of responsibilities, Administrators' politics, Academic staff, Job satisfaction, Universities

Introduction

Academic staff job satisfaction can be described as the degree of need satisfaction derived from an employee evaluation of the intrinsic and extrinsic aspect of his or her job. Such intrinsic and extrinsic aspects of job satisfaction include salary, working conditions, policy, responsibility and career advancement (Herzberg, 1959). Responsibility as one of the indicators of job satisfaction has implications on academic staff. This is because delegation of responsibility is a powerful source of empowerment.

According to Ameer, Bhatti and Baig (2014) employee empowerment is canvassed and founded on the premise that giving employee skills, resources, authority, opportunity, motivation and holding them responsible and

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accountable for outcomes of their action will contribute to their job satisfaction and performance. This is in line with Elnaga and Imran (2014) admonition that when employees are empowered through responsibility and control over decision making with respect to their work, their confidence and self-reliance will increase which stimulates job satisfaction and level of productivity. Responsibility involves the satisfaction an employee derives from having control over his work and that of others. Therefore, empowering academic staff with meaningful responsibility, work control and decision making is expected to be a strong enabler of employee satisfaction with their job and invariably might enhance their performance. Wonah, Egbula, and Ekpo, (2016) opined that the success of any institution depend purely on administrative heads who oversee the affair of such organization. Thus, the departmental head work tirelessly to ensure that the organizational goals are achieved. To achieve the realization of the objective of establishing such organization, there is need for the departmental head to administer their function effectively in order to ensure proper task performance by the non academic staff. Okorji, and Unachukwu, (2014) defined administration as a social process that concerned with identifying, motivating controlling and unifying formally and informally organised human and national resource within an integrated system designed specifically to accomplish predetermined goals. Thus, administration of department by the head of department has to do with getting things done by staff in order to achieve a definite purpose in an organisation. The idea of goal achievement or task performance by the head of department is central to the concept of administration.

According to Ogunsaju (2012) viewed administration as the driving force that propels all organisation process. It also concerned with several varieties tasks. It initiates and directs activities control and monitors the functioning of the different organs of the system. Administration is the component part of management that concerned with promoting achievement of organisation objectives by carefully using available resources both material and non-material in order to accomplish predetermined goals.

Nwankwo, (2017) described administration as a careful and systematic arrangement use of human and material resource situation and opportunities for the achievement of specific objectives. Peretomode, (2011) defined administration as the performance of executive duties, the carrying out of policies or decisions to fulfil a purpose and the controlling of the day to day running of the organisation. Thus, administration occurs in almost every human organisation. Therefore, it influences all the directions to pursue goals or outcomes within the organisation. Nzomiwu (2017) affirmed that the head of department is primarily in charged with the development of each and every staff in the department. This is because the worker is at the centre of the organizational process and all activities in the organization should aim at developing his total personality to the fullest.

The misconceptions of the link between politics and education seem to stem from the common misunderstanding of the meaning of politics, and what constitutes a 'political act. Okunamiri (2010). The concept of politics has most often been interpreted to mean simply the unbridled struggle for power among individuals or groups. Thus defined, politics was perceived as "a dirty game" too unwholesome for the sanitized humanitarian act of education. Such narrow or restricted conception of politics was common with the perception of the earlier politicians and the traditional political scientists (Wonah, 2016). Political interference in education, noncompliance in agreement, inconsistency in policy formulation and implementation and unnecessary delay in payment of salaries and other emolument of academic staff (Anashie & Aniah, 2018).

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According to Wonah (2019) Educational qualification plays a major role in determining the type of job an individual will get and the performance on it which is regarded as the service delivery generally. Conceptually, educational qualification refers to the level of intellectual attainment by an individual with a back-up of certificates obtained via such intellectual attainment (Njeuma, 2009). According to the author, educational qualification determines the nature of services to be delivered in institutions and organizations. The assertion further buttresses the fact that educational qualification is the core basis for employment in view of the services expected to be delivered by the academician in context.

Okonkwo (2019) defined educational qualification as an academic ladder that distinguished one another in the circle of the academia. The researcher maintained that educational qualification is prescribed in an act of participating in an examination or a course with a successful completion of such educational, professional and vocational programme with a passing grade. Uvah (2005) viewed educational qualification as means of categorization of what simplifies the academician into strata or levels based on their individual attainment academically. The researcher further buttresses the educational qualifications in the following: doctor of philosophy degree (Ph.D.), masters' degree, bachelor degree, diploma/National certificate of education, senior school certificate, and first school leaving certificate. According to the researcher, individuals are equivocally categorized based on the above levels of educational qualifications to distinguish them as a form of specification in the society.

In their study, Gudo *et al.* (2011) found that tribalism (ethnicity) was an impediment to equal employment opportunities in Nigeria universities. They found that tribalism and nepotism were the factors which mainly prevented equal opportunities in universities in Nigeria. As a result, they interpreted that negative ethnicity and nepotism were obstacles to an objective search for senior university officers and had the adverse potential of denying universities competent human resource for quality management. However, their study did not investigate the relationship of the challenge of negative ethnicity and nepotism to overall academic staff job satisfaction in Nigeria universities.

According to Asogwai, Oboebulem, Ugwoke., Okeke, Ugwuanvi, and Diara (2018) The influence of ethnicity on job satisfaction has received great attention in job satisfaction studies with inconsistent findings. Ethnicity refers to a group of people who are distinct on the basis of a presumed common genealogy or ancestry with peculiar cultural characteristics handed down from generation to generation which might include; lifestyle, beliefs, language, norms, religion, traits, forms of dress, music, food, attitudes and values (Riggins, 2012). The ethnicity of Nigeria is varied and as such, it has been difficult, if not impossible, to determine the exact number of ethnic groups in Nigeria. Thus, about three hundred ethnic groups comprise the population of Nigeria and only three ethnic groups have attained "ethnic majority status" in their respective regions namely the Hausa-Fulani in the North, the Yoruba in the South West and the Igbo (Ibo) in the South East, Nigeria (Rakov, 2010). Each ethnic group has its own unique culture and values. Such differences among people could influence their overall behavior and level of satisfaction in the workplace. Studies investigating the relationship between ethnicity and job satisfaction reported contradictory findings. Abu-Bader (2008) found out that ethnicity was related to job satisfaction of employees. Hikaru (2010) on the contrary, noted that ethnicity was not related to job satisfaction.

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Therefore, whether the ethnic background is related to job satisfaction of academic staff in the location of this study is yet to be ascertained.

Job satisfaction is a significant driver of employee performance and invariably institutional success. This is because job satisfaction reflects employee well-being and their perception towards their job. An employee in the context of this study implies academic staff in public universities who are principal actor in the delivering of the institutional goals of teaching, research and community service.

Despite the crucial role of academic staff in human capital development and nation building, academic staff welfare and concern in Nigeria tertiary institutions particularly the public universities appears to have been neglected and treated with disdain by the government at all level in Nigeria. The lackadaisical attitude of Nigeria government towards academic staff welfare and concern has created a discord and constant faceoff between federal government and academic staff. Such dissatisfaction among academic staff is reflected in the incessant industrial strike by consortium of academic staff union of universities. It is against this background that the researchers intend to examine administrators' politics of delegation of responsibilities and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Delegation of responsibilities by University administrators are considered significant because it facilitate effective achievement of university goals. Regrettably, from the researchers experience and observation, it has shown that some of the academic staff are dissatisfied with their job as a result of not been involved in any of responsibilities delegated the university administrators. This may likely be as a result of lack of job qualification for the position or because of ethnicity politics. This seems to manifest in staff been inefficient and unproductive in the system. Although attempt like introduction of politics equality, fairness and equal balance in delegation of responsibilities to the qualified persons. Despite all these efforts made by the university administrators, the problem of poor delegation of responsibilities still persist. It is against this backdrop that the researchers intend to examine administrators' politics of delegation of responsibilities and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to examine administrators' politics of delegation of responsibilities and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study intends to find out whether:

- i. Delegation of responsibilities base on educational qualification relate with academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State.
- ii. Delegation of responsibilities base on ethnicity relate with academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State.

Research questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. In what ways do delegation of responsibilities base on educational qualification relate with academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State?

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ii. In what ways do delegation of responsibilities base on ethnicity relate with academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State?

Research hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- i. There is no significant relationship between delegation of responsibilities base on educational qualification and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between delegation of responsibilities base on ethnicity and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State.

Methodology

The study adopted the Correlational research design. Population of the study consist of one hundred and forty (141) heads of Department from two public Universities in Cross River State were selected for the study The selection was done through census sampling technique.

The instrument used for the data collection was questionnaire titled: Administrators' Politics of Delegation of Responsibilities and Academic Staff job Satisfaction Questionnaire (APDRASSQ) was developed by the researchers and was validated by experts in administration in higher education and measurement and evaluation in the department of Educational foundations in Faculty of Education, University of Calabar, Calabar. The instrument was divided into two Sections. A and B. section A sought for respondents demographic data such as name of school, sex, rank, and qualification. Section B consisted of ten (10) items constructed in a four (4) point modified Likert scale ranging from strongly Agree (SA) 4 points, Agree (A) 3 points, Disagree (D) 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) 1 point. Data collected were subjected to statistical analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25 was used for data analysis and the results are presented as follows.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between delegation of responsibility base on educational qualification and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State. The calculated result is presented in table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Correlation analysis of the relationship between delegation of responsibility base on educational qualification and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State (n=141).

Variables	Mean	Std.Dev.	r cal.	P-value
Delegation of responsibility base on educational qualification	15.80	2.720	.844**	.001
Academic staff job satisfaction	15.62	2.869		

• Significant at .05 level; df = 139 critical $-r.159$

The result in table 1 revealed that the calculated r-value of .844 ** was significantly greater than the critical value of .159 when tested at .05 level of significance with 139 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is a significant relationship between delegation of responsibility base on educational qualification and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State.

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Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between delegation of responsibility base on ethnicity and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State. The calculated result is presented in Table two.

Table 2: Summary of Correlation analysis of the relationship between delegation of responsibility base on ethnicity and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State (n=141).

Variables	Mean	Std.Dev.	r cal.	P-value
Delegation of responsibility base on educational qualification	16.00	2.652	.801**	.001
Academic staff job satisfaction	15.62	2.869		

• Significant at .05 level; df = 139 critical –r.159

The result in table 2 revealed that the calculated r-value of .801 ** was significantly greater than the critical value of .159 when tested at .05 level of significance with 139 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is a significant relationship between delegation of responsibility base on ethnicity and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State.

Discussion of the findings

The result of the hypothesis one stated that there is a significant relationship between delegation of responsibility base on educational qualification and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State. The result finding is in agreement with the finding of Wonah(2019), Okonkwo (2009) and (Njeuma, 2009) whose stated that educational qualification plays a major role in determining the type of job an individual will get and the performance on it which is regarded as the service delivery generally. Conceptually, educational qualification refers to the level of intellectual attainment by an individual with a back-up of certificates obtained via such intellectual attainment. According to the author, educational qualification determines the nature of services to be delivered in institutions and organizations. The assertion further buttresses the fact that educational qualification is the core basis for employment in view of the services expected to be delivered by the academician in context.

The result of hypothesis two stated that there is a significant relationship between delegation of responsibility base on ethnicity and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State. The findings of this study is in consonant with the findings of Asogwai,Oboebulem,Ugwoke.,Okeke,Ugwuanvi,and Diara(2018), Riggins, (2012) and Gudo *et al.* (2011) whose studies opined that the influence of ethnicity on job satisfaction has received great attention in job satisfaction studies with inconsistent findings. Ethnicity refers to a group of people who are distinct on the basis of a presumed common genealogy or ancestry with peculiar cultural characteristics handed down from generation to generation which might include; lifestyle, beliefs, language, norms, religion, traits, forms of dress, music, food, attitudes and values

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the data collected and analyzed, the study concluded that there is a significant relationship between delegation of responsibility base on educational qualification and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State. Also, that there is a significant relationship between delegation of responsibility base on ethnicity and academic staff job satisfaction in universities in Cross River State, Nigeria.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, it was recommended that:

- i. University management should delegation of responsibility base on educational qualification.
- ii. University management should not delegation of responsibility base on ethnicity.

References

- Ahmad, R., Ing, H. E., & Bujang, S. (2014). Relationship between selected factors of job satisfaction and job performance among workers at palm oil industries. *International Review of Management and Business Research*, 3(3), 1751–1766.
- Ameer, M. H., Bhatti, S., & Baig, S. (2014). Impact of employee empowerment on job satisfaction. *Developing Country Studies*, 4(9), 114–125.
- Asogwai, U. D., Oboebulem, A., Ugwoke, F. C., Okeke, F. C., Ugwuanvi, J. C., & Diara, C. F. (2018). Information and communication technology skills and job satisfaction among academic staff in colleges of education. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, 13(6), 3500–3506. <http://www.ripublication.com>
- Elnaga, A. A., & Imran, A. (2014). The impact of employee empowerment on job satisfaction. *American Journal of Research Communication*, 2(1), 13–26.
- Gudo, O. C., Oanda, O. I., & Olel, M. A. (2011). Role of institutional managers in quality assurance: Reflections on Kenya's university education. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 1(2), 113–124.
- Herzberg, F. (1959). *The motivation to work*. New York: John Wiley.
- Hikaru, M. (2010). *Relationship among perceived ethnic discrimination, job attitudes, and behaviors* (Master's thesis, San Jose State University). Retrieved December 5, 2012.
- Njeuma, D. L. (2009). *Reforming a national system of higher education: The case of Cameroon*. Association for the Development of Education in Africa (ADEA) Working Group on Higher Education.
- Nwankwo, J. I. (2007). *Educational administration*. New Delhi: Anmol Publishers.
- Nwaogu, J. (2006). *A guide to effective supervision of instruction in Nigeria schools*. Enugu: Fourth Dimension Press.
- Nzomiwu, J. P. C. (2007). *Dynamic of educational administration and management: The Nigerian perspective*. Onitsha: Meks Publishers.
- Ogunsaju, S. (2002). *Education supervision perspective and practices in Nigeria*. Ife: University of Ife Press.
- Okonkwo, M. O. (2009). Education for nation building achievement of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). *The Voice of the Government*, 1(1), 97–100.

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- Okorji, P., & Unachukwu, G. (2014). Development of educational administration and management. In P. Unachukwu & P. Okorji (Eds.), *Educational management: A skill building approach*. Anambra: Rex Charles & Patrick, Book Smith House, Harmony Place Publishers.
- Okunamiri, P. O. (2010). *The politics of education: The Nigerian experience*. Owerri: FASMEN Communication Press.
- Peretomode, U. F. (2001). *General principles of school administration, planning and supervision*. Lagos: Joja Educational Research and Publishers.
- Rakov, S. A. (1990). Ethnicity in Nigeria. *African Postcolonial Literature in English*. Retrieved from <http://www.postcolonialweb.org>
- Riggins, S. H. (1992). *Ethnic minority media: An international perspective*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publishers.
- Saleem, M. A., & Imran, M. (2014). Relationship between job satisfaction and job performance: A case study of universities of Peshawar District (KPK) Pakistan. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(31), 314–324.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2009). *World Conference on Higher Education: The new dynamics of higher education and research for societal change and development*. Paris: UNESCO. <http://www.unesco.org/fileadmin/MULTIMEDIA/HQ/ED/ED/pdf/WCHE2009/FINAL%20COMMUNIQUE%20WCHE%202009.pdf>
- Uvah, I. I. (2005). Educational qualification and institutional stability in the Nigerian university system. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Administration and Planning*, 5(1), 1–11.
- Wonah, F. A. (2016). Political influence and educational provision in Nigeria. In J. Okon, B. Akuegwu, & E. Uko (Eds.), *Emerging issues in educational administration, planning and supervision*. Calabar: University of Calabar Press.
- Wonah, F. A. (2019). *Academic staff demographic variables and quality service delivery in universities in Cross River State, Nigeria* (Master's thesis, University of Calabar). Lambert Academic Publishing. ISBN: 978-613-9-94611-2.
- Wonah, F. A., Egbula, E. O., & Ekpo, E. E. (2016). Administrative function of departmental heads and non-academic staff task performance in University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Administration, Planning and Research*, 8(2), 77–83.